

Graph Neural Networks for Effective Prediction of Mechanical Response in Composite Structures with Models using Unstructured Meshes

Luca Patrignani¹, Silvestre T. Pinho²

¹ Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London, Exhibition Rd, South Kensington, London SW7 2AZ, UK
Email: l.patrignani@imperial.ac.uk, web page: <https://www.pinholab.com>

² Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London, Exhibition Rd, South Kensington, London SW7 2AZ, UK
Email: silvestre.pinho@imperial.ac.uk, web page: <https://www.pinholab.com>

Keywords: Graph Neural Networks; Finite Element Analysis; Numerical analysis; Mechanical properties; Laminates

ABSTRACT

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are emerging as a transformative approach for predicting mechanical response in composite structures by naturally encoding unstructured finite element meshes as graphs. While traditional finite element analysis provides trusted solutions for structural mechanics problems, it encounters significant computational and scalability bottlenecks. We present a methodology that extends the MeshGraphNets framework with frequency-controlled hybrid local-global attention mechanisms that addresses the challenge of capturing both local behaviour around geometric discontinuities and global strain field patterns in composite laminates. Our approach integrates with industrial FEA workflows through an automated Abaqus-to-GNN pipeline that converts FEM simulations to graph representations. We validate our approach on Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) laminate plates with open holes. The results demonstrate exceptional predictive accuracy ($R^2 = 0.9775$) while achieving a 200× computational speedup over traditional finite element analysis. This represents a fundamental shift from computation-intensive iterative solving to near-instantaneous prediction for composite structure design applications.

1. Introduction

The aviation industry faces critical sustainability challenges as a major contributor to CO2 emissions [1]. This drive for sustainability is spurring novel aircraft configurations, particularly those incorporating alternative fuels, which requires a fundamental shift in design methodologies demanding high-performance predictive models of full-scale aircraft structures [2]. Finite Element Analysis offers trusted mesh-based solutions for structural mechanics problems involving partial differential equations [3]. However, FEA faces scalability and computational issues in large-scale applications, especially when various configurations need separate simulations, resulting in high computational costs [4]. Graph Neural Networks emerge as a natural solution by effectively representing and processing data on graphs [5, 6]. Pfaff et al. (2021) [7] developed a framework for learning mesh-based simulations using graph neural networks, demonstrating that GNNs can capture complex physical interactions through graph adjacencies while remaining resolution-independent [8]. While GNNs have been successfully applied to predict mechanical responses in structural components [9, 10], significant challenges remain. Current methodologies exhibit limited accuracy when addressing severe stress concentrations, particularly in complex geometries

with geometric discontinuities [11]. Additionally, they encounter difficulties with long-range information propagation during message passing, which can lead to over-smoothing issues [9]. In this work, we address these limitations by developing a novel GNN architecture that extends the MeshGraphNets model [7] with enhanced frequency-controlled hybrid local-global attention mechanisms. We validate our approach on Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) laminate plates with open holes, demonstrating excellent performance with 200× computational speedup while maintaining high accuracy for strain concentration prediction.

2. Graph Neural Networks for Mesh-Based Physics

Graph Neural Networks extend the concept of convolution to irregular topologies using message-passing mechanisms [5]. Unlike Convolutional Neural Networks which function on fixed neighborhood structures, GNNs can process unstructured mesh data directly. The process consists of three sequential operations: encoding, processing, and decoding. The **encoding** transforms raw node and edge features into latent representations through learnable transformations. The **processing** propagates information through the graph via iterative message exchange between connected nodes. The **decoding** maps the refined embeddings to target predictions. Full details will be given at the conference. For comprehensive information, please refer to the forthcoming journal paper to be submitted for publication (Patrignani, L., & Pinho, S. T., 2025).

Figure 1: Graph Neural Network for Mesh-Based Physics architecture overview showing the three-stage encoder-processor-decoder framework.

3. Automated FEA-to-GNN Pipeline

We developed an automated pipeline that transforms FEA simulations into GNN training data, mapping the traditional *input-solver-output* workflow directly to supervised learning’s *problem-solution* pairs. The pipeline encompasses sample generation, mesh-to-graph conversion, solver execution, and solution extraction as shown in Figure 2. This framework generates three tensor structures: node tensor encoding spatial coordinates and boundary conditions, edge tensor representing connectivity and geometric relationships, and target tensor containing solution field variables from FEA outputs. The automated framework transforms weeks of manual preprocessing into hours of computation, enabling rapid exploration across diverse structural mechanics problems.

Figure 2: Automated FEA-to-GNN pipeline architecture transforming FEA workflow to GNN paradigm.

4. GNN Model for Composite Structures

This work develops a specialized GNN architecture for predicting longitudinal strain fields in CFRP open-hole tension plates. We extend the MeshGraphNets framework with frequency-controlled hybrid local-global attention mechanisms to capture both local behavior around geometric discontinuities and global strain field patterns.

4.1. Problem Setup

As shown in Figure 3, plate dimensions are randomly sampled with length and height ranging from 100 to 200 *mm*. Hole radius varies between 10 and 20 *mm*, with position factors ranging from 0.3 to 0.7 of plate dimensions. Applied displacement magnitude varies from 1 to 2 *mm*, generating 500 distinct samples with symmetric [0°/45°/90°/-45°]s layup configuration.

Figure 3: CFRP open-hole tension plate configuration showing variable features.

4.2. Data Representation

Node features incorporate geometric and physical information:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = [x_i, y_i, \mathbb{I}_{\text{fixed}}, \mathbb{I}_{\text{hole}}, \mathbb{I}_{\text{displaced}}, u_{\text{applied}}]^T \quad (1)$$

Edge features capture local geometric relationships:

$$\mathbf{e}_{ij} = [x_i - x_j, y_i - y_j, \|\mathbf{r}_{ij}\|_2]^T \quad (2)$$

Target variables represent longitudinal strain: $y_i = \varepsilon_{xx,i}$

4.3. Model Architecture

As illustrated in Figure 4, the model implements a three-stage encoder-processor-decoder framework with hybrid attention mechanisms.

Figure 4: Complete GNN architecture with encoder-processor-decoder framework and attention mechanisms.

The processor implements message-passing with local attention at each step and global attention applied every M layers. Local attention coefficients weight neighboring information, while global attention enables direct long-range interactions following transformer architecture principles. The full details of the mathematical formulations and extended analyses of the GNN framework will be presented in the forthcoming journal paper to be submitted for publication (Patrignani, L., & Pinho, S. T., 2025).

4.4. Hyperparameter Optimization

Systematic hyperparameter tuning was performed using Optuna with Tree-structured Parzen Estimator sampling. Key findings identified learning rate and batch size as primary performance drivers. The optimal configuration achieved validation loss of 0.2621.

4.5. Results

Figure 5 demonstrates exceptional model accuracy with $R^2 = 0.9775$ and RMSE of 0.00022. The regression line closely follows the ideal diagonal, indicating minimal systematic bias across the full strain range. Training convergence analysis demonstrates substantial performance improvement with our hybrid attention architecture compared to standard message-passing, achieving approximately 64% improvement in training performance and 73% improvement in validation performance. The computa-

tional performance analysis reveals 200× speedup compared to traditional FEA, requiring only 0.5% of the original simulation time while maintaining high accuracy.

Figure 5: Predicted vs. actual strain correlation demonstrating excellent accuracy ($R^2 = 0.9775$).

5. Conclusions

This work presents a novel Graph Neural Network architecture that successfully addresses critical limitations in traditional finite element analysis for composite structural mechanics. By extending the Mesh-GraphNets framework with hybrid local-global attention mechanisms, we demonstrate significant computational acceleration while maintaining high predictive accuracy for strain field prediction in CFRP open-hole tension plates. Our key contributions include: (1) a hybrid attention mechanism that effectively captures local and global mechanical behaviour, achieving $R^2 = 0.9775$ accuracy while avoiding over-smoothing issues; (2) a 200× speedup compared to traditional finite element analysis; (3) an automated Abaqus-to-GNN pipeline that transforms weeks of manual preprocessing into hours of computation, facilitating seamless integration with existing commercial workflows. The demonstrated capability to predict mechanical response with minimal feature engineering requirements, combined with seamless FEA integration, positions this approach as an enabling tool for accelerating composite structure design and analysis in aerospace applications. The framework’s extensibility to diverse structural mechanics problems using identical architectures represents a significant step toward practical surrogate modeling capabilities for engineering simulation.

Future research directions include extending the framework to progressive damage modeling and exploring multi-scale GNN architectures. For comprehensive details on computational complexity analysis, extended mathematical formulations, and hyperparameter optimization studies, please refer to the forthcoming journal paper to be submitted for publication (Patrignani, L., & Pinho, S. T., 2025).

References

- [1] David S Lee, David W Fahey, Agnieszka Skowron, Myles R Allen, Ulrike Burkhardt, Qi Chen, Sarah J Doherty, Sarah Freeman, Piers M Forster, Jan Fuglestedt, et al. The contribution of global aviation to anthropogenic climate forcing for 2000 to 2018. *Atmospheric environment*, 244:117834, 2021.
- [2] Vittorio Cipolla, K Abu Salem, G Palaia, V Binante, and Davide Zanetti. A doe-based approach

- for the implementation of structural surrogate models in the early stage design of box-wing aircraft. *Aerospace science and technology*, 117:106968, 2021.
- [3] Olgierd Cecil Zienkiewicz, Robert Leroy Taylor, and Jian Z Zhu. *The finite element method: its basis and fundamentals*. Elsevier, 2005.
- [4] S. T. Pinho, M. Matos, R. O. S. S. Costa, A. Ibbotson, and M. Ostergaard. Enabling multiscale analysis of very large composite structures. In *8th ECCOMAS Thematic Conference on the Mechanical Response of Composites*, 2021. doi: 10.23967/composites.2021.123.
- [5] Franco Scarselli, Marco Gori, Ah Chung Tsoi, Markus Hagenbuchner, and Gabriele Monfardini. The graph neural network model. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, 20(1):61–80, 2008.
- [6] Will Hamilton, Zhitao Ying, and Jure Leskovec. Inductive representation learning on large graphs. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 30, 2017.
- [7] Tobias Pfaff, Marc Fortunato, Alvaro Sanchez-Gonzalez, and Peter W Battaglia. Learning mesh-based simulation with graph networks. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 8459–8468. PMLR, 2020.
- [8] Chunhao Jiang and Nian-Zhong Chen. Graph neural networks (gnns) based accelerated numerical simulation. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 123:106370, 2023.
- [9] Rutwik Gulakala, Vaishnav Bhaskaran, and Marcus Stoffel. A generative learning and graph-based framework for computing field variables in finite element simulations. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 428:117111, 2024.
- [10] Marco Maurizi, Chao Gao, and Filippo Berto. Predicting stress, strain and deformation fields in materials and structures with graph neural networks. *Scientific reports*, 12(1):21834, 2022.
- [11] Jiaqian Wu, Chaoyu Du, Benjamin Dillenburger, and Michael Anton Kraus. Fast prediction of stress distribution: A gnn-based surrogate model for unstructured mesh fea. In *Proceedings of the IASS 2024 Symposium: Redefining the Art of Structural Design*, volume 2024. International Association for Shell and Spatial Structures, 2024.